

Supplementary Material

Hospital Genomic Surveillance and Resistance Profiling of Multidrug-Resistant Acinetobacter baumannii: Clonal Diversity and Virulence Insights

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Figure S1. Phylogenetic reconstruction of *Acinetobacter baumannii* strains including the reference genome of *Acinetobacter Baumannii* and SAMPLE-34.

Figure S2. Phylogenetic representation of *Acinetobacter baumannii* strains which provides a visualisation of clusters even in the presence of SAMPLE-34. The tree branches highlighted in green have a support ≥ 0.9 .

Figure S3. Phylogenetic representation of *Acinetobacter baumannii* strains including *Acinetobacter baumannii* reference genome and excluding SAMPLE-34.

Figure S4. Graph depicts the distribution of virulence factors as predicted by PathoFact.

Supplementary Table 1-CheckM

SAMPLE_ID	Bin Id	Marker lineage	# genomes	# markers	# marker sets	0	1	2	3	4	5	Completeness (%)	Contamination (%)	Strain heterogeneity	Overall Quality
SAMPLE-11	0	Acinetobacter baumannii (6)	20	1018	298	1	1011	6	0	0	0	99,95	0,61	0,00	High
SAMPLE-12	0	Acinetobacter baumannii (6)	20	1018	298	1	1015	2	0	0	0	99,95	0,25	0,00	High
SAMPLE-14	0	Acinetobacter baumannii (6)	20	1018	298	9	1008	1	0	0	0	98,40	0,17	0,00	High
SAMPLE-15	16	Acinetobacter baumannii (6)	20	1018	298	7	1010	1	0	0	0	98,73	0,17	0,00	High
SAMPLE-16	24	Acinetobacter baumannii (6)	20	1018	298	14	999	5	0	0	0	97,99	0,53	0,00	High
SAMPLE-17	12	Acinetobacter baumannii (6)	20	1018	298	1	1015	2	0	0	0	99,95	0,25	0,00	High
SAMPLE-18	3	Acinetobacter baumannii (6)	20	1018	298	9	1008	1	0	0	0	98,40	0,17	0,00	High
SAMPLE-19	1	Acinetobacter baumannii (6)	20	1018	298	1	1015	2	0	0	0	99,95	0,25	0,00	High
SAMPLE-1	0	Acinetobacter baumannii (6)	20	1018	298	1	1015	2	0	0	0	99,95	0,25	0,00	High
SAMPLE-20	19	Acinetobacter baumannii (6)	20	1018	298	1	998	19	0	0	0	99,95	2,29	68,97	High
SAMPLE-21	3	Acinetobacter baumannii (6)	20	1018	298	7	1005	6	0	0	0	99,70	0,61	0,00	High
SAMPLE-22	17	Acinetobacter baumannii (6)	20	1018	298	1	991	26	0	0	0	99,95	3,21	76,47	High
SAMPLE-23	3	Acinetobacter baumannii (6)	20	1018	298	1	1012	5	0	0	0	99,95	0,53	0,00	High
SAMPLE-24	2	Acinetobacter baumannii (6)	20	1018	298	1	1011	6	0	0	0	99,95	0,61	9,09	High
SAMPLE-25	0	Acinetobacter baumannii (6)	20	1018	298	2	1014	2	0	0	0	99,87	0,25	0,00	High
SAMPLE-26	2	Acinetobacter baumannii (6)	20	1018	298	859	118	41	0	0	0	10,66	1,35	98,25	Low

SAMPLE-27	1	Acinetobacter baumannii (6)	20	1018	298	859	127	32	0	0	0	10,66	0,45	92,42	Low
SAMPLE-28	21	Acinetobacter baumannii (6)	20	1018	298	24	992	2	0	0	0	98,73	0,34	50,00	High
SAMPLE-29	28	Acinetobacter baumannii (6)	20	1018	298	6	1011	1	0	0	0	99,07	0,17	0,00	High
SAMPLE-2	17	Acinetobacter baumannii (6)	20	1018	298	1	1011	6	0	0	0	99,95	0,61	0,00	High
SAMPLE-30	33	Acinetobacter baumannii (6)	20	1018	298	1	1010	7	0	0	0	99,95	0,75	0,00	High
SAMPLE-31	1	Acinetobacter baumannii (6)	20	1018	298	2	1014	2	0	0	0	99,62	0,25	0,00	High
SAMPLE-32	0	Acinetobacter baumannii (6)	20	1018	298	1	1011	6	0	0	0	99,95	0,61	0,00	High
SAMPLE-33	31	Acinetobacter baumannii (6)	20	1018	298	1	1014	3	0	0	0	99,95	0,28	20,00	High
SAMPLE-34	12	Acinetobacter baumannii (6)	20	1018	298	1	1015	2	0	0	0	99,95	0,25	0,00	High
SAMPLE-35	30	Acinetobacter baumannii (6)	20	1018	298	24	993	1	0	0	0	98,73	0,17	0,00	High
SAMPLE-36	6	Acinetobacter baumannii (6)	20	1018	298	2	1010	6	0	0	0	99,84	0,61	0,00	High
SAMPLE-37	1	Acinetobacter baumannii (6)	20	1018	298	1	1015	2	0	0	0	99,95	0,25	0,00	High
SAMPLE-38	1	Acinetobacter baumannii (6)	20	1018	298	44	973	1	0	0	0	96,97	0,17	0,00	High
SAMPLE-39	15	Acinetobacter baumannii (6)	20	1018	298	12	1005	1	0	0	0	98,40	0,17	0,00	High
SAMPLE-3	28	Acinetobacter baumannii (6)	20	1018	298	1	1011	6	0	0	0	99,95	0,61	0,00	High
SAMPLE-40	30	Acinetobacter baumannii (6)	20	1018	298	1	1011	6	0	0	0	99,95	0,61	0,00	High
SAMPLE-41	33	Acinetobacter baumannii (6)	20	1018	298	14	1003	1	0	0	0	98,65	0,17	0,00	High
SAMPLE-42	18	Acinetobacter baumannii (6)	20	1018	298	3	971	44	0	0	0	99,50	5,64	83,33	Medium

SAMPLE-43	10	Acinetobacter baumannii (6)	20	1018	298	16	1001	1	0	0	0	97,39	0,17	0,00	High
SAMPLE-44	0	Acinetobacter baumannii (6)	20	1018	298	6	1006	6	0	0	0	98,95	0,61	0,00	High
SAMPLE-45	5	Acinetobacter baumannii (6)	20	1018	298	6	1011	1	0	0	0	99,07	0,17	0,00	High
SAMPLE-46	5	Acinetobacter baumannii (6)	20	1018	298	1	1014	3	0	0	0	99,95	0,29	0,00	High
SAMPLE-47	0	Acinetobacter baumannii (6)	20	1018	298	10	1006	2	0	0	0	98,95	0,25	0,00	High
SAMPLE-48	0	Acinetobacter baumannii (6)	20	1018	298	1	1011	6	0	0	0	99,95	0,61	0,00	High
SAMPLE-5	16	Acinetobacter baumannii (6)	20	1018	298	1	1011	6	0	0	0	99,95	0,61	0,00	High
SAMPLE-6	5	Acinetobacter baumannii (6)	20	1018	298	1	1015	2	0	0	0	99,95	0,25	0,00	High
SAMPLE-7	13	Acinetobacter baumannii (6)	20	1018	298	546	471	1	0	0	0	38,67	0,17	0,00	Low
SAMPLE-8	27	Acinetobacter baumannii (6)	20	1018	298	1	1011	6	0	0	0	99,95	0,61	0,00	High

Supplementary Table 2-GTdbTK

SampleID	classification	Closest Genome Reference
SAMPL E-1	d__Bacteria;p__Pseudomonadota;c__Gammaproteobacteria;o__Pseudomonadales;f__Moraxellaceae;g__Acinetobacter;s__A_cinetobacter baumannii	GCF_009759685.00
SAMPL E-11	d__Bacteria;p__Pseudomonadota;c__Gammaproteobacteria;o__Pseudomonadales;f__Moraxellaceae;g__Acinetobacter;s__A_cinetobacter baumannii	GCF_009759685.01
SAMPL E-12	d__Bacteria;p__Pseudomonadota;c__Gammaproteobacteria;o__Pseudomonadales;f__Moraxellaceae;g__Acinetobacter;s__A_cinetobacter baumannii	GCF_009759685.02
SAMPL E-14	d__Bacteria;p__Pseudomonadota;c__Gammaproteobacteria;o__Pseudomonadales;f__Moraxellaceae;g__Acinetobacter;s__A_cinetobacter baumannii	GCF_009759685.03
SAMPL E-15	d__Bacteria;p__Pseudomonadota;c__Gammaproteobacteria;o__Pseudomonadales;f__Moraxellaceae;g__Acinetobacter;s__A_cinetobacter baumannii	GCF_009759685.04
SAMPL E-16	d__Bacteria;p__Pseudomonadota;c__Gammaproteobacteria;o__Pseudomonadales;f__Moraxellaceae;g__Acinetobacter;s__A_cinetobacter baumannii	GCF_009759685.05
SAMPL E-17	d__Bacteria;p__Pseudomonadota;c__Gammaproteobacteria;o__Pseudomonadales;f__Moraxellaceae;g__Acinetobacter;s__A_cinetobacter baumannii	GCF_009759685.06
SAMPL E-18	d__Bacteria;p__Pseudomonadota;c__Gammaproteobacteria;o__Pseudomonadales;f__Moraxellaceae;g__Acinetobacter;s__A_cinetobacter baumannii	GCF_009759685.07
SAMPL E-19	d__Bacteria;p__Pseudomonadota;c__Gammaproteobacteria;o__Pseudomonadales;f__Moraxellaceae;g__Acinetobacter;s__A_cinetobacter baumannii	GCF_009759685.08
SAMPL E-2	d__Bacteria;p__Pseudomonadota;c__Gammaproteobacteria;o__Pseudomonadales;f__Moraxellaceae;g__Acinetobacter;s__A_cinetobacter baumannii	GCF_009759685.09
SAMPL E-20	d__Bacteria;p__Pseudomonadota;c__Gammaproteobacteria;o__Pseudomonadales;f__Moraxellaceae;g__Acinetobacter;s__A_cinetobacter baumannii	GCF_009759685.10
SAMPL E-21	d__Bacteria;p__Pseudomonadota;c__Gammaproteobacteria;o__Pseudomonadales;f__Moraxellaceae;g__Acinetobacter;s__A_cinetobacter baumannii	GCF_009759685.9
SAMPL E-22	d__Bacteria;p__Pseudomonadota;c__Gammaproteobacteria;o__Pseudomonadales;f__Moraxellaceae;g__Acinetobacter;s__A_cinetobacter baumannii	GCF_009759685.8
SAMPL E-23	d__Bacteria;p__Pseudomonadota;c__Gammaproteobacteria;o__Pseudomonadales;f__Moraxellaceae;g__Acinetobacter;s__A_cinetobacter baumannii	GCF_009759685.7
SAMPL E-24	d__Bacteria;p__Pseudomonadota;c__Gammaproteobacteria;o__Pseudomonadales;f__Moraxellaceae;g__Acinetobacter;s__A_cinetobacter baumannii	GCF_009759685.6
SAMPL E-25	d__Bacteria;p__Pseudomonadota;c__Gammaproteobacteria;o__Pseudomonadales;f__Moraxellaceae;g__Acinetobacter;s__A_cinetobacter baumannii	GCF_009759685.5
SAMPL E-26	d__Bacteria;p__Pseudomonadota;c__Gammaproteobacteria;o__Pseudomonadales;f__Moraxellaceae;g__Acinetobacter;s__A_cinetobacter baumannii	GCF_009759685.4

SAMPL E-44	d__Bacteria;p__Pseudomonadota;c__Gammaproteobacteria;o__Pseudomonadales;f__Moraxellaceae;g__Acinetobacter;s__A cinetobacter baumannii	GCF_009759685 .14
SAMPL E-45	d__Bacteria;p__Pseudomonadota;c__Gammaproteobacteria;o__Pseudomonadales;f__Moraxellaceae;g__Acinetobacter;s__A cinetobacter baumannii	GCF_009759685 .15
SAMPL E-46	d__Bacteria;p__Pseudomonadota;c__Gammaproteobacteria;o__Pseudomonadales;f__Moraxellaceae;g__Acinetobacter;s__A cinetobacter baumannii	GCF_009759685 .16
SAMPL E-47	d__Bacteria;p__Pseudomonadota;c__Gammaproteobacteria;o__Pseudomonadales;f__Moraxellaceae;g__Acinetobacter;s__A cinetobacter baumannii	GCF_009759685 .17
SAMPL E-48	d__Bacteria;p__Pseudomonadota;c__Gammaproteobacteria;o__Pseudomonadales;f__Moraxellaceae;g__Acinetobacter;s__A cinetobacter baumannii	GCF_009759685 .18
SAMPL E-5	d__Bacteria;p__Pseudomonadota;c__Gammaproteobacteria;o__Pseudomonadales;f__Moraxellaceae;g__Acinetobacter;s__A cinetobacter baumannii	GCF_009759685 .19
SAMPL E-6	d__Bacteria;p__Pseudomonadota;c__Gammaproteobacteria;o__Pseudomonadales;f__Moraxellaceae;g__Acinetobacter;s__A cinetobacter baumannii	GCF_009759685 .20
SAMPL E-7	d__Bacteria;p__Pseudomonadota;c__Gammaproteobacteria;o__Pseudomonadales;f__Moraxellaceae;g__Acinetobacter;s__A cinetobacter baumannii	GCF_009759685 .21
SAMPL E-8	d__Bacteria;p__Pseudomonadota;c__Gammaproteobacteria;o__Pseudomonadales;f__Moraxellaceae;g__Acinetobacter;s__A cinetobacter baumannii	GCF_009759685 .22

SAMPLE-38	abaumannii_2	-	Pas_cpn60(2)	Pas_fusA(2)	Pas_gltA(2)	Pas_pyrG(2)	Pas_recA(2)	Pas_rplB(2)	Pas_rpoB(-)
SAMPLE-39	abaumannii_2	2	Pas_cpn60(2)	Pas_fusA(2)	Pas_gltA(2)	Pas_pyrG(2)	Pas_recA(2)	Pas_rplB(2)	Pas_rpoB(2)
SAMPLE-40	abaumannii_2	2	Pas_cpn60(2)	Pas_fusA(2)	Pas_gltA(2)	Pas_pyrG(2)	Pas_recA(2)	Pas_rplB(2)	Pas_rpoB(2)
SAMPLE-41	abaumannii_2	2	Pas_cpn60(2)	Pas_fusA(2)	Pas_gltA(2)	Pas_pyrG(2)	Pas_recA(2)	Pas_rplB(2)	Pas_rpoB(2)
SAMPLE-42	abaumannii_2	2	Pas_cpn60(2)	Pas_fusA(2)	Pas_gltA(2)	Pas_pyrG(2)	Pas_recA(2)	Pas_rplB(2)	Pas_rpoB(2)
SAMPLE-43	abaumannii_2	2	Pas_cpn60(2)	Pas_fusA(2)	Pas_gltA(2)	Pas_pyrG(2)	Pas_recA(2)	Pas_rplB(2)	Pas_rpoB(2)
SAMPLE-44	abaumannii_2	2	Pas_cpn60(2)	Pas_fusA(2)	Pas_gltA(2)	Pas_pyrG(2)	Pas_recA(2)	Pas_rplB(2)	Pas_rpoB(2)
SAMPLE-45	abaumannii_2	2	Pas_cpn60(2)	Pas_fusA(2)	Pas_gltA(2)	Pas_pyrG(2)	Pas_recA(2)	Pas_rplB(2)	Pas_rpoB(2)
SAMPLE-46	abaumannii_2	2	Pas_cpn60(2)	Pas_fusA(2)	Pas_gltA(2)	Pas_pyrG(2)	Pas_recA(2)	Pas_rplB(2)	Pas_rpoB(2)
SAMPLE-47	abaumannii_2	2	Pas_cpn60(2)	Pas_fusA(2)	Pas_gltA(2)	Pas_pyrG(2)	Pas_recA(2)	Pas_rplB(2)	Pas_rpoB(2)
SAMPLE-48	abaumannii_2	2	Pas_cpn60(2)	Pas_fusA(2)	Pas_gltA(2)	Pas_pyrG(2)	Pas_recA(2)	Pas_rplB(2)	Pas_rpoB(2)
SAMPLE-5	abaumannii_2	2	Pas_cpn60(2)	Pas_fusA(2)	Pas_gltA(2)	Pas_pyrG(2)	Pas_recA(2)	Pas_rplB(2)	Pas_rpoB(2)
SAMPLE-6	abaumannii_2	2	Pas_cpn60(2)	Pas_fusA(2)	Pas_gltA(2)	Pas_pyrG(2)	Pas_recA(2)	Pas_rplB(2)	Pas_rpoB(2)
SAMPLE-8	abaumannii_2	2	Pas_cpn60(2)	Pas_fusA(2)	Pas_gltA(2)	Pas_pyrG(2)	Pas_recA(2)	Pas_rplB(2)	Pas_rpoB(2)